

VOL. V, ISSUE II

INTERNATIONAL NEWSLETTER

OCTOBER 2025

ISSN (Print) 2799-192X ISSN (Online) 2799-1407

NEWSCREATE

FEATURING INNOVATIONS, BEST PRACTICES, & ACCOMPLISHMENTS

AI

PINAGPALA PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB REG. NO. 3269
DTI BUSINESS REG. NO. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ BUSINESS PERMIT NO. 8183
PINAGPALAPUBLISHINGSERVICES@GMAIL.COM
+639684666397

THE LASTING LEGACY OF MY FATHER

Johna G. Belardo
Assistant Professor 2
Benguet State University

He is gone. His passing sent shockwaves throughout the entire university community. He had just recently retired and was only beginning to adjust to a life outside the academic world—a world where he had devoted more than half of his life. Life, indeed, is short, but he filled his years with purpose and passion at the university.

To most, he was known as Sir Doming. To me, he is—and always will be—my Dad. As I was growing up, I was aware that he was a respected teacher, but it was only much later that I truly came to understand the profound impact he had on those around him. His undergraduate students often described him as strict and demanding, while those in the graduate program saw him as a supportive mentor, a dedicated thesis and dissertation adviser, and an exceptionally intelligent educator. This contrast highlighted the depth and range of his influence.

Many of his students recounted how he would enter the classroom with nothing but a piece of chalk. He delivered lectures with such fluency and command that by the end of the class, students found their notebooks filled with notes—even though he had barely written anything on the board. His ability to speak with clarity and depth amazed students, not only for the volume of knowledge shared but also for the insight gained in such a short span of time.

One student once remarked, “You’ll know when Sir Garin is around. His presence is felt in the room.” Indeed, his influence was palpable, extending far beyond mere authority. He often told his students that a teacher must be genuine: “Smile if you must. Show eye contact. Be angry if you must, because a teacher cannot pretend.” For him, authenticity was essential—you cannot fake the art of guiding others. He also believed in always being prepared—being at least a chapter ahead of the students—ensuring his teaching was grounded in both honesty and expertise.

During an interview, he shared his approach to motivating students. He explained that he begins by using extrinsic motivators—such as checking attendance for the first three meetings and assigning regular activities and homework. Once he observes that students are becoming genuinely interested in the lesson, he shifts to intrinsic motivation. At this stage, he takes time to explain the purpose behind what they are learning, helping students see the value in the knowledge being taught. He believed that when students start attending class regularly out of genuine interest, that is when a teacher has truly succeeded in motivating them.

Beyond his lectures, my father was a mentor whose influence shaped students’ personal and professional lives. He constantly emphasized maintaining a positive attitude and a deep respect for the teaching profession.

He believed that a teacher must wholeheartedly accept the role they have chosen, embracing each student as a unique individual—clients deserving of understanding, not judgment. He strongly discouraged comparing students to one another. Instead, he urged teachers to reflect honestly on their own teaching methods, reminding them that what works today might not work tomorrow.

To him, teaching was a dynamic journey—one of constant preparation, adaptation, and sincere care for each learner. These were not just philosophies; they were lived experiences, and those who studied under him absorbed these lessons deeply.

Ironically, despite being his child, I never had the opportunity to sit in his classroom and be directly taught by him. Now that he is gone, I realize the magnitude of what I missed.

It is a unique kind of absence—not simply missing someone—but missing the chance to learn directly from their expertise. Yet, watching others benefit from his mentorship made me appreciate how much he shaped the world around us.

My father's influence wasn't confined to the classroom; he was also a devoted sports coach who dedicated countless hours to the softball and slo-pitch fields. Serving as both a player and a coach, he led his teams to multiple championships in Intramurals, BBEAL, CARASUC, NSCUAA, and various open tournaments—earning accolades that brought tremendous pride to the school. His unwavering commitment to sports and the positive impact he had on his athletes were acknowledged beyond the school community, as he was formally recognized by the Province during the Benguet CARES program for his outstanding contributions to the field of sports.

His athletes admired his disciplined approach and unwavering commitment to excellence. They noted how his values—fair play, discipline, humility—shaped not only their athletic skills but also their character.

For many athletes, Sir wasn't just a coach. He was a mentor whose lessons extended beyond physical training into life itself. He saw each athlete's potential and pushed them to embrace both their strengths and their struggles. He motivated them to strive harder, to build trust, and to support each other—always leading by example.

Even those who were not in his classroom felt the weight and warmth of his legacy through the standards he upheld and the community he built.

Despite all these accolades, the most personal part of his legacy is this: he was my dad. And though I never sat in his class, his influence still found its way to me.

I came to realize that many of the teachers who guided us in our elementary, high school, and senior high years were themselves mentored by him. Through their words and actions, his influence reached us. The same values—integrity, dedication, humility—were echoed in the way they taught and nurtured us.

In this way, my dad's guidance became an integral part of my learning journey, even if I only encountered it secondhand.

As the master of ceremonies called, "Dr. Dominador Sarmiento Garin, Professor VI, 42 years in service," I watched from my computer, unable to be present because of quarantine restrictions during the pandemic. I saw my father receive a large plaque of appreciation, a testament to his dedication. His legacy endures—not just through the lessons he delivered, but through the countless lives - teachers, deans, principals, directors, chairpersons, and different leaders of the community- he touched and transformed. Now, they are the ones who guide and nurture me as I continue my own journey.

Through them, I continue to receive the wisdom my father once shared. The values of teaching, mentoring, coaching, leadership, and community he instilled are very much alive in the people he influenced.

My Dad was more than an educator. He was a coach, a mentor, a builder of character. His teaching extended beyond textbooks and lesson plans. It was about curiosity, resilience, and the lifelong journey of learning.

His story is a powerful reminder that teaching is not confined to four walls—it is a ripple that echoes across generations. Though I never sat in my father's classroom, his teachings have found their way to me through the voices of those he inspired.

He was the teacher I never had, but he is, in every sense, the mentor I always needed.